

Evaluation of India: A Reference Annual

BIBLIOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

Title	India 2019
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INTRODUCTION

INDIA 2019- A REFERENCE ANNUAL IS A COMPREHENSIVE DIGEST OF THE COUNTRY'S PROGRESS IN DIFFERENT FIELDS. THE BOOK DEALS WITH ALL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT - FROM RURAL TO URBAN, INDUSTRY TO INFRASTRUCTURE, SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY TO ART AND CULTURE, ECONOMY, HEALTH, DEFENCE TO EDUCATION AND MASS COMMUNICATION etc.

Also it is an authoritative compilation of the complete information about the current affairs of the country, which includes important dignitaries, state policy, public schemes and important data related to demographics, trade, economy and others.

SCOPE

It is national in scope covers information on various Topics and development sectors of India.

This book covers following fields of country-

1. Land and the People
2. National Symbols
3. Polity
4. Agriculture
5. Culture and Tourism
6. Basic Economic Data
7. Commerce
8. Communications and Information Technology
9. Defence
10. Education
11. Energy
12. Environment
13. Finance
14. Corporate Affairs

15. Food and Civil Supplies
16. Health and Family Welfare
17. Housing
18. India and the World
19. Industry
20. Justice and Law
21. Labour
22. Mass Communication
23. Planning
24. Rural and Urban Development
25. Scientific and Technological Developments
26. Transport
27. Water Resources
28. Welfare
29. Youth Affairs and Sports
30. States and Union Territories
31. Diary of National Events
32. General Information

TREATMENT

- The above chapters involve information about physiography of India, Demographic terminologies and Census 2011 data. It has data about various aspect of National flag, State Emblem and Anthem of nation (along with English translation).
- Elaborates executive part of the government with rights and basic features of the Constitution.
- Details programmes and policies related to agriculture in India, different agricultural sectors, recent initiatives and policies launched by GOI.
- Different functions for conservation of ancient cultural heritage and promotion of art and culture (tangible and intangible both).
- Chapters has three sections of communication forms i.e. Posts, Telecommunications and Information Technology with a topic of cyber security.
- Also a chapter of Security scenario of India, defence undertakings, training for defence services, etc.
- Education system of country with new policies. Chapters also included conventional and nonconventional energy sector in the country.
- GOI Investment on programmes for the youth and incentive schemes for sportspersons.
- Data on implementation of India's environment and forest policies and programmes relating to conservation of country's natural resources as well as sustainable development.

- Discusses welfare schemes for the SC/ ST/ OBC/ Minorities/ Women/ Children.
- A separate chapter of important facts and figures about each states and union territories of India.
- A diary of national events throughout the year and a chapter for general information of country which contains Presidents, Vice Presidents, PMs, CJIs etc lists plus list of awards distributed among civilians as well as forces of the nation.
- Appendices includes GOI, ministers, members of parliament etc. and abbreviations used for parties.

ARRANGEMENT

- All the content is arranged in chapters which is in classified order.
- The lists of general information chapter is in chronological order except sahitya akademi awards and national highways list which is in Statewise alphabetical order.
- In appendices member of parliament list is also in Statewise alphabetical order.

FORMAT

Print format:

- A single volume handbook.
- Legible printing.
- Text Size is suitable for readers.
- Enough spacing between lines and words.
- Bold headings and Subheadings, Some data in tabular form.
- A strong Paperback Binding.

Other format:

- Available in ebook format from Publication Division's official website <https://www.publicationsdivision.nic.in>
- Also in Amazon kindle edition.

SPECIAL FEATURES

The information about member of parliament along with his/her State and party/group in appendices is value added to the book.

LIMITATIONS

- Not available in Online or CD-ROM version.

- Very few pictorial and graphical representation.
- Large number of pages for local Advertisement in such a authentic source.

CONCLUSION

This reference annual is very useful book for anybody who is looking for the country's information on working of Government, it's functioning, various bodies and programmes etc. The sections on general knowledge, current affairs, sports and important events, are a must read for comprehensive understanding of these fields. With it's authenticity of facts and data, the book is also a treasure for students, researchers and academicians.

REFERENCES

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